

Storage and Long Term Preservation Strategies in PRACE Tier-1 Datacentres

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(SARA, SNIC, CaSToRC, CINES)

Abstract

In SARA, SNIC-NSC, CaSToRC and CINES, different strategies to store and preserve academic data produced as part of research projects are in place. Even if they are fairly similar, the policies and technologies which have been deployed to manage those data have a few differences which will be detailed. The way they address the increasing need for long time archival storage, in combination with the ever increasing size and rate of data produced will be also described, as well as data sharing problems in joint research efforts where large data sets need sharing.

1. Storage and long term preservation of data at SARA

1.1. The SARA CA and its intended usage

SARA's HPC Central Archive (CA) is a mass storage facility for long-term preservation of large data sets produced in academic research projects that are of particular relevance to (Dutch) academic communities. To be more specific about the groups that can benefit from the service: the CA currently stores data that were produced on several incarnations of the Dutch supercomputing facility and various other academic HPC facilities at SARA. In addition, the SARA CA stores data from DEISA and PRACE projects of Dutch academic groups that were not necessarily produced at a SARA facility, but e.g. on a Tier-0 system or Tier-1 system at the site of a PRACE partner.

The datasets stored at the CA are quite heterogeneous in size and in retrieval patterns, though infrequent retrieval of datasets dominates. The archive facility dates back to 1991, when it was introduced as a dedicated archive for the Dutch national supercomputer – then a CRAY YMP system. The notion of what constitutes a large data set has changed considerably since 1991, and with it the implementation of the archive facility has evolved in several ways, but until 2007 the facility remained dedicated and technically very tightly coupled to incarnations of the Dutch national supercomputer. Since 2007 the facility is indeed “central” in the sense that all HPC compute and visualization facilities at SARA can access the CA to store or retrieve data. With the Dutch supercomputer integrated in DEISA since 2004, it happened occasionally – even before 2007 – that datasets produced in DECI projects of Dutch groups running on an HPC system at another site were entered into the SARA archive – necessarily via the Dutch super computer as an intermediate hop.

Since the advent of PRACE and the integration of Tier-0 and Tier-1 facilities across Europe into an HPC “ecosystem” the number projects with off-site produced data that will be archived at the SARA CA is expected to grow substantially. One aspect of the recent restructuring of the CA in 2011 was the already obvious need to better facilitate and streamline external access. A service node for external access, “archive.sara.nl”, independent of any of the HPC facilities, was added. Users can access the SARA CA directly from an offsite location, through a number of protocols, ssh/scp/sftp and GridFTP, to store and retrieve data, or to logically reorder or physically relocate already stored data. The number of methods for external access will be extended with project specific https-based interfaces and other suitable generic protocols.

The SARA CA still contains a considerable number of old datasets that are fairly small by today’s standards next to more recent datasets produced in Dutch “Data Challenge” projects and DEISA/PRACE projects which have sizes ranging from 30 TB (ENTRAIN [1]) to 50 TB (Essence [2], OWLS [3]), or even 110 TB (CosmoGrid/GBBP [4]).

1.2. Architectural overview of the SARA CA

The current CA facility is based on a tiered storage environment which is built around a small cluster of seven relatively simple nodes using clustered XFS (CXFS) file systems. All data enter and leave the SARA CA as files on the on-line disk storage of one these file systems. A parallel version of SGI’s Data Migration Facility (DMF) software provides automated, transparent^a, hierarchical storage management – migration to and from other media, such as tapes or secondary disk storage – for these file systems.

Figure 1: Software stack, key components

CXFS is SGI’s implementation of a SAN-shared file system. XVM, SGI volume manager software, is used to create a single, aggregate, logical volume from multiple hardware RAID5 LUNs on the SAN, for each CXFS file system. Striping rather than concatenation of hardware LUNs is generally used as the method of aggregation, as striping adds significantly to the performance of the file system^b. Since RAID5 redundancy is already applied on the storage hardware level, RAID5 or mirroring (RAID1) configuration options on the level of the XVM volume manager are not used. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** shows the key components of the software stack from the top, where the end-user enters, down to the disk and tape hardware.

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. shows a more detailed architectural overview of the current (since June 2011) SARA CA environment. All nodes of the CXFS cluster have multiple SAN fibers to the disk storage of the CXFS file systems. Some nodes of the CXFS cluster – those labeled “cdm1” – “cdm3”- act exclusively as NFS servers exporting the CXFS file systems over several 10Gbit/s and 1Gbit/s network links to NFS clients, i.e.: nodes of SARA HPC and visualization facilities as well as the external service node. Automated policies for hierarchical storage management are in place, but ultimately the user knows best which files are wanted on-line and when. It is standard policy to give the end user control over this matter and to provide some tooling to overrule the effect of automated policies. Over the NFS protocol however it cannot be communicated whether a file in an exported file system has its data blocks offline or on-line. Therefore all NFS client hosts are also equipped with SARA rdmf – i.e.: “remote DMF” – client software, which brings elementary

^a By “transparent” we mean that the file system always shows the complete picture of everything that is available in the file system. The semantics of the file system are not changed by the DMF layer. A difference in performance between on-line and off-line files may be noticeable, but nothing special or different has to be done by the user to access off-line files. When data of an off-line file must be read, DMF is automatically triggered to “unmigrate” the file to disk.

^b On the other hand, concatenation can be, and has been, used as a way to grow online disk capacity of a file system “on the fly”, while more structural methods of re-allocation storage resources, all requiring downtime and maintenance, are pending.

hierarchical storage management primitives, functionality to list and manipulate the on-line/off-line status of files, to the NFS client hosts^c.

Other nodes of the CXFS cluster act exclusively as “tape servers” – labeled “ctm1” –“ctm3” - and have 4Gbit/s SAN connections to a number of tape drives for migrating between the tape backend and the disk storage of the file systems. A single node – labeled “cdmf” - is meta-data server for the file systems and assumes various other orchestrating and communication roles.

The functionality provided by the seven nodes of the CXFS cluster can in principle be provided by a large monolithic server node that combines all functions. In previous incarnations of the CA this was actually the case. The combination of *clustered XFS* + *parallel DMF* together is used to implement a migration facility that is distributed and more scalable in several independent dimensions.

An important policy of the SARA CA, directed at ensuring a high level of reliability and availability, is to store dual copies of data on tapes in two distinct “volume groups”^d that are kept at geographically different datacentre locations. The “local” SAN fabric, depicted in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, which connects the tape servers to the tape drives, actually spans two datacentre locations that are about 35 KM apart. The tape drives are concentrated in two tape libraries: one is in Amsterdam, the other is in Almere. The core switches in the datacentres in Amsterdam and Almere are connected via long distance links over two independent dark fibers. The connection between the dark fibers and the rest of the SAN at each datacentre is based on coarse wavelength-division multiplexing (CWDM) technology. The SAN switches on either side effectively “see” four 4 Gbit/s fiber channel connections to the other side.

^c The DMF software provides tools to monitor and manipulate the on-line/off-line status of files directly on nodes of the CXFS-DMF environment only. The SARA rdmf tools are modeled as closely after these tools as possible. They presuppose an NFS environment in which a particular path on a client can be mapped to a particular NFS server on which the same absolute path actually denotes the same - NFS-exported – files. Essentially the rdmf tools are “network wrappers” that export the functionality of native the DMF tools to a wider client environment.

^d An older, but perhaps more apt and generic term than “volume group” to use here would be: “media specific process” (MSP). An MSP does not necessarily have to denote a group of volumes in a tape library. DMF is more generic than that: it can utilize very different media as well: disk, a remote FTP store.

Figure 2: SARA CA, architectural overview

Both in Amsterdam and in Almere the tape back-end is a StorageTek SL8500 Library, currently equipped with StorageTek T10KB drives. The SARA CA is *not* the only service that makes use of these back-ends. It shares them with two other services:

1. SARA also provides a grid-enabled storage element for that is mainly used by the Lofar project [5] and the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) projects at CERN [6]. For the LHC projects, SARA is one of CERN's Tier-1 sites.
2. Until recently SARA had a remote backup service for mostly academic clients, dating from the days that such services were not yet commercially available^e.

The data volume of the grid-enabled storage element is currently over 3 PB – substantially that of the SARA CA. The grid mass storage service to a considerable extent also uses the same software technology but it has its own DMF instance, its own CXFS cluster, its own separately organized front-end with dedicated light paths to CERN, etc. The remote backup service is based on IBM TSM software, and thus organized very differently. Both services do not fall within the scope of this document. They should however be briefly noted here, because it must be granted that their sharing of the same tape back-end infrastructure has made for some flexibility and economics of scale effects that have been beneficial for the total cost of ownership of all services – the SARA CA included. It is for instance possible to temporarily shift a tape drive from the SARA CA to the LHC Tier-1 environment, or vice versa.

^e The commerce of the service has been transferred to a company. The data currently still remain in the same back-ends, but will eventually be phased out, thus leaving the SARA back-end for the CA and LHC tier-1 service.

1.3. Hierarchical storage management: location of data and meta-data

To understand some of the SARA CA policies and tools to be discussed below, some details about the handling of data and meta-data by the hierarchical storage management system must be explained. Note that the dual copy on tape created by the DMF is a copy of the file's *data* only. All *meta-data*, describing ownership, access permission, file name and the logical position of a file within a file system tree structure with named directories, reside in the file system on disk and are *never* copied to tape by the hierarchical storage management software.

Figure 3: DMF bfid linking file meta-data residing in the file system with meta-data residing in the DMF database. Directory meta-data (the left column in the CXFS block) always remain in the file system on disk only and consequently never have a bfid.

The hierarchical storage management software adds some meta-data overhead for itself. Every file managed by DMF gets a unique binary file identifier (**bfid**) that is stored in a DMF database. The bfid is also stored in the on disk i-node, together with a migration status attribute, and thus is the crucial linking pin between DMF and other meta-data residing in the file systems. The DMF database keeps one table with records that relate a bfid to an instance on tape and its library server section. Since the default policy is to have two copies, there are normally two such records per file^f. One or more contiguous tape stretches, “chunks”, on one or more tape volumes, together constitute a copy of the file contents on tape. A second (type of) table^g contains records that associate tape chunks - described in terms their tape volume ID and location on that tape - with the tape copy instance they belong to. And finally, a third table in the DMF database holds records that describe a tape volume ID in terms of its location, type, volume group, and several usage statistics. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** shows the organization of DMF meta-data and file system meta-data with the bfid as linking pin between the two.

The DMF database lives on a separate dedicated file system. For robustness, journaling system that tracks the transactions to the database lives on yet another file system that is dedicated to this purpose.

1.4. Backup of the archive: Integration of hierarchical storage management and meta-data backup

Archiving and backup are two distinct facilities for users. But users rightly expect that the SARA CA itself is safeguarded against calamities by the availability of backups. By itself the dual copies on tape do not constitute a complete backup for situations where the file system on disk and/or the DMF database is lost. Reliable backups are provided by exploiting some characteristics of the hierarchical storage management implementation and complementing it with the necessary meta-data backups:

1. A daily backup of the DMF database
2. A daily “meta-data only” full backup of all file systems with hierarchical storage management
3. A daily backup of those files that are stored in the archive but are either considered too small to migrate to dual tape copies or have not been migrated yet.

The DMF database (and journals) is backed up separately. A procedure has been developed that creates a backup of items 2 and 3 in a single run per file system. To keep the backup overhead small and the backup window short, the number of files to be included with the meta-data must be kept at a minimum. Rather than migrating to

^f For files that are below a certain size there is an additional copy in the global disk cache or “disk MSP” (see section 1.5, below), three records per file, rather than two, are normal: two for the copies on tape plus a third one for a copy in the disk cache.

^g Actually there is a “tape chunk table” for each MSP or “volume group” that has been defined. Conceptually this is not different from having a single table in which the MSP name or volume group is an added field that becomes part of the - then composite - primary key.

tape only when on-line disk space becomes tight, the hierarchical storage management software is configured to scan frequently for files that are newly added to the archive. It schedules the new or updated files immediately for dual copying to tape, but without necessarily discarding the on disk copy when the instances on tape have been created. This ensures that data that have put in the archive indeed have a backup well within 24 hours. It also ensures that the overwhelming majority of new files in the archive have been pre-migrated before the complementary procedures run and that they can indeed be complemented with i-node only data. Once created, both datacenter locations store their own copies of the complementary DMF database backups and meta-data backups.

Besides being a necessary backup complement the “meta-data only backup” of a file system is also actively used as a tool that allows extensive restructuring of disk resources, i.e.: for splitting or merging file systems, and/or migrating to new hardware in a fairly small maintenance window. The backup contains the bfid's of all migrated files and the DMF database is structured in such a way that it is void of any relative or absolute path assumptions. Thus a “meta-data only backup”, or a sub-tree of it, can be restored to any file system that is brought under DMF control. When the “meta-data only restore” is complete, the file system is directly usable - although it will initially have a performance penalty, since 100% of its file data-blocks are initially still off-line. As soon as files are accessed, “unmigrating” starts.

1.5. Main strategies for efficient handling of data on tape

A large quantity of the data in the archive must be preserved for a long time but are accessed rather infrequently. Although there are some exceptions, many data in the SARA CA are not entered as data sets available to the general public but remain the intellectual property of the research groups that produced them. Typically, data are produced, e.g. by a PHD student working on a particular project that has its place in a longer term program of a research group.

Often a large portion of the data is retrieved when an article by the PHD student is reviewed or published and some additional questions have to be answered. After that the data remain usually untouched until they are retrieved at the start of follow up projects in the research program, and access rights have been arranged for one or more new PHD students of the group. The data or a subset that is needed more frequently during the course of follow-up projects generally does *not* have to stay on-line in the CA during the course of the project, as it is staged to the HPC compute platform where the follow-up project runs.

Recently we observe a gradual shift in the population of archive users, from data-owners archiving their data mainly for themselves, their close collaborators and immediate successors, to data-owners archiving datasets for limited, moderated, public availability. The data-retrieval is still expected to be infrequent, though slightly more frequent than before, because a limited number independent parties - rather than one - have an interest in the data. We believe that the continuation of this trend will have a limited impact on storage strategies, but may have more consequences for the retrieval interfaces that we offer (see section 1.7, below).

For the longer term preservation of vast quantities data that are infrequently retrieved, tape is a very adequate medium. The initial investment in an automated tape library is undoubtedly higher than that in a disk array, but the economic lifetime is much longer too. The first tape library at SARA, a StorageTek Powderhorn, remained productive from 1991 to 2007 without ever extending its physical storage capacity or “robot resources”. However, during this period, tape drives and tape cartridges were several times gradually replaced by newer generation of drives and cartridges compatible form factors but a much larger data capacity per tape. Thus, old data are regularly converted to newer tape media. In 2010, the last cartridges with a storage capacity of 200 GB, and their associated drives with a sustained streaming bandwidth of 30 MB/s., were phased out. Their successors - the current T10KB cartridges - have a storage capacity of 1TB and the drives sustain a streaming bandwidth of 120MB/s. The latest generations of form factor compatible cartridges and associated tape drive types have a capacity of 4-5 TB, c.q. a bandwidth of 240-250 MB/s.

Not only do such media conversions expand the data capacity and enhance performance, they also have a data-integrity preserving side effect that is important in its own right. Although there are integrity tests of randomly sampled tapes, data that have not been retrieved for some time may have come to reside on a bad tape without anybody noticing. During the media conversion process, the old source tapes involved are necessarily systematically read. Any flawed tapes will be discovered. Such incidents automatically result in the restoration of “full redundancy” by re-creation of a dual copy on the new target media from the single instance on old media that remained intact.

Liberal use is made of the possibility to define specific “volume groups” for projects that produce large data sets. This amounts to pre-allocating sets of tape cartridges in both datacenters and subsequently adding policy rules that state that data of particular UIDs and/or GIDs can only be migrated to tapes belonging to particular volume groups. Especially when data are produced and archived gradually in the course of a project they could very

well end up dispersed over a multitude of tapes. When the complete dataset is retrieved later, this would result in very large mount overhead. The use of volume groups effectively precludes this. Moreover, it leads to complete datasets also being identifiable at the level tape cartridges, which enables planning of media conversion for specific projects.

There are no fixed criteria or policies for deciding whether or not a project is allocated its own dedicated volume groups. To do so is an ad hoc decision, but nonetheless a grounded one for which the reasons have become evident in the technical evaluation that takes place during the intake of a project, in which there is a lot of communication with the scientists involved over their specific needs for resources – including storage resources.

For small files the overhead of retrieving from tape is comparatively large. Therefore, for small files, with a size below 1.75 MB (but larger than 16K), there is a policy in place to keep an additional third copy on a “disk MSP”, i.e. on secondary disk storage. The disk MSP instance is configured to be the first to be tried when “unmigration” of a small offline file is requested. The disk MSP is in fact a global disk cache for small files, shared by all file systems under DMF control. Its maximum capacity is currently 22 TB, the volume currently used by cached small files with a size between 16 KB and 1.75MB is 12 TB.

The slightly odd number of 1.75 MB, constituting the current upper file size limit for “small files” getting a copy in the global disk cache is of course a very tuned number. What is considered a small file evolves over time, with the capacity of and mount/dismount overhead of time of tape cartridges, and is also influenced by what users actually put in the archive. Periodically the total storage capacity used by files of different size classes is investigated and this leads to global overviews such as the one presented in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** which e.g. shows that in 2007 90% of the number of files archived by national super computer projects were of a size less than 4 MB. At the same time the storage capacity used by this 90% of files was less than 7% of the total storage capacity. For the short term, the capacity of the disk cache is fixed and such overview can suggest a change in the operational definition of a small file. For the longer term the data are used to determine what the capacity of the disk cache should be.

Figure 4: Cumulative distributions, of used storage capacity and of number of files stored, over file size classes. The “Super capacity” and “Superfiles” graphs are associated with the SARA CA. Other graphs denote other services using the same tape back-end.

Finally the smallest files, with a size below 16KB, are never migrated by DMF at all. Putting such small files in the archive is discouraged. Nevertheless we have them, but in terms of data volume they are negligible.

1.6. Usage of on-line disk space

The CA archive setup always needs a file system on disk front-end for data. But for infrequently accessed datasets its on-line disk capacity can be heavily oversubscribed. As a bare minimum, the on disk file systems need to have at least the capacity to accommodate the largest file of its data sets on-line in its entirety. More frequently accessed files need much more on-line disk capacity for the service to have adequate responsiveness to requests. In total the SARA CA currently stores about 0.8 PB of data (more than 1.5 PB in dual tape copies), while the net capacity of all on-line disk space for the CXFS file systems is about 35 TB.

Theoretically the best solution is perhaps to have a single file system with a single pool of on-line disk space. At any particular time only a very limited number of the infrequently accessed datasets are actively accessed. In one single pool all active projects would be able to access all resources and these could be optimally divided among the active projects. In practice there are several reasons why this does *not* work too well. For one thing, having more file systems simply allows for more parallel processing, like the static division of labor between NFS servers noted in section 1.2 and depicted in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** Another, related, objection against a single file system is that all i-nodes would be collected in this file system. With oversubscription of disk space, the amount of i-nodes will become prohibitively large for efficient operation. Several operations on i-nodes within a single file system must be atomic and are serialized.

Furthermore, the optimal division of allocation resources over active projects out of a single pool cannot do without some tool for establishing quota of on-line disk capacity. The standard file system disk quota administration of used disk blocks is of course a likely candidate, but in its present state it is very hard to use in conjunction with DMF, because DMF and the quota subsystem are totally unaware of each other. To ensure that archiving of new data is always possible, an amount of free disk space on a file system must be always maintained. The policy in place for this is necessarily a file system level policy. When on-line disk space becomes tight, when the free space threshold set for the file system is reached, DMF will start deleting the disk blocks of files on that file system that have dual copies on tape, and the priorities of its behavior can be customized in terms of file size, file age, time since last access, group or user ownership, etc. - but *not* in terms of amount of on-line disk usage and quota. Having different file systems allows the CA at least to have different levels for the free space threshold, and different priorities, per file system.

In practice we have different file systems of different sizes and varying degrees of oversubscription of the on-line disk space that roughly corresponds to the need of different projects. Often projects cycle through various stages in which data are predominantly produced, analyzed, archived, retrieved, etc. It is for example possible to set the free space threshold for a file system to zero or nearly zero, if the projects on that file system, are in a phase in which they do not produce new data, but retrieve a lot. Projects that are predominantly in an archiving phase can be well served with a file system with fairly modest on-line disk capacity and a high free space threshold.

The allocation of projects to file systems and of disk resources to file systems is regularly reviewed, and if need be adapted, even at times when replacement or extending of disk hardware resources is not due. In the past file systems have been merged as well as split. Merged, e.g. to enlarge the total on-line disk space associate with a file system. Split, e.g. because the number of i-nodes was growing towards a situation where the time window needed for the above described “i-node only” backup procedure became too large. In situations where extending the disk resources is not an option, backup and restore of “i-node only file system dumps” has proven to be an essential tool for substantial restructuring of disk resources and file systems.

In the SARA CA setup, a file system is an obligatory passage point for streaming large quantities of data to and from tape. Users are taught the overhead of handling 1000 files of 10 MB is huge, in terms of discrete per file operations (opening, closing, updating i-node date and size fields, etc.), compared to the handling of a similar data volume that is organized in 10 files of 1 GB. On the one hand, users are encouraged to pack smaller files into larger units of at least 1GB when storing something in the archive. On the other hand, we do recognize that this is not always feasible for some file sets and we mediate at least the retrieval cost of smaller files by a global disk MSP. On file systems where this is appropriate, standard file system quota *for i-node maxima per user*, are used to provide the user with an incentive to make more balanced and responsible decisions about what can be packed and what not.

It is clear that, especially with data sets being produced on PRACE Tier-0 systems with a significantly larger compute capacity than our local compute environments, the size of single data sets is growing rapidly. Currently the largest on-line disk volume is 18 TB. This simply has become too small. The highest priority now – and indeed planned extension - for the SARA CA, is the addition with more, and most of all larger, primary file systems to temporarily hold larger quantities of on-line simultaneously to smoothen the process of data retrieval.

From the primary investigators owning the data we know that the new data sets still will be infrequently accessed, however more frequent than used to be the case. Moreover, they will be accessed from more heterogeneous locations, because public access – albeit moderated public access - to the data is permitted to several parties. The bandwidth that these parties have available on their own Internet uplink will vary considerably. This implies that retrieval in some cases takes longer and that there sometimes will be a need to browse that data and to make appropriate selections for retrieval. To appropriately facilitate this, there is a need to extend the “temporary on-line-ness” to several weeks rather than hours or days, and to have a large data set completely on-line - rather than partly – for pre-retrieval browsing purposes.

1.7. The file system as the primary user interface and other interfaces

The primary user interface to the archive is still the file system interface – nowadays exported via NFS. In terms of functionality the file system interface is sufficient and complete. Users get interactive access to an NFS client and can add, delete, or move items, or browse and search their archive sections with familiar tools. Under the relative root of their directory they can order items in a tree like system of directories and subdirectories that makes sense to them, as on any file system. As mentioned above, the archive uses several file systems and the underlying structure may be changed. Because of a simple layer of two levels of indirection by means of symbolic links the user always sees the same logical view; an archive facility starting at a unified root “/archive”, with his or her archive logically located underneath at “/archive/<username>”.

The fact that DMF is transparent, that the archive has the same look and feel of any other ordinary file systems is comfortable for most archive users. But in all fairness it is probably best regarded as a mixed blessing, since the very transparency of DMF also facilitates sub-optimal behavior of users that sometimes indeed remain totally oblivious of the migration status of their files and inflict severe I/O performance penalties upon themselves.

When large files are archived or retrieved over the NFS link performance target are usually met. However, because the same channel is used for data transfers and commands to browse the NFS mounted file systems, the interactive response is degraded when there is a lot of data traffic to the point where the archive file systems appear to be very sluggish” for the browsing user.

As is common in shared file system environments, the user administrations of all hosts having access to the file system have to be integrated to ensure that UIDs and GIDs consistently denote the same users and groups in all contexts that access the shared file systems. The SARA CA systems are all integrated into the SARA Central User Administration (CUA), as are the NFS client systems. Thus ownership, group ownership, and permissions for granting or denying access to archived items are simply regulated by means of standard file system meta-data. If non-interactive access by means of scp or sftp is used, users authenticate against the same CUA and thus access the NFS mounted file system with the same identity and associated permissions.

For a secondary interface, like gridFTP – digital certificate based - access, some extra work is done: a “grid-map file” is maintained to map certificate distinguished names of known users to CUA UIDs and GIDs that can be compared to the UIDs and GIDs that are contained in the meta-data of the archive file systems. Likewise, for custom project specific https based interface solutions, UID and GID mapping solutions are needed. So far such custom solutions have only been used on a very limited scale. The UID mapping problem has been circumvented in a not very scalable way:

- A custom https server instance is started, on a non-privileged IP port of “archive.sara.nl”^h, with a CUA UID and GID of a user associated with the project thus with permissions to access the relevant data. The UID and GID of the https process and its child processes does not change.
- Subsequently, the https server instance has its own local authentication - usually password based and possibly augmented with additional access constraints in terms of a limited set of allowed IP addresses for clients to connect from.

We already noted a gradual shift to archiving of data that are kept for public availability or at least for availability to several parties rather than one. This implies that the archived data can also be retrieved by people that have had little or no prior contact with the original producer, that are not likely to have the opportunity to engage in informal communications about, which particular details are stored where, in what files, etc. With this shift, the flexible but informal file system interface, with its supposedly intuitive and descriptive tree-ordering, perhaps augmented with an occasional “README file”, becomes less appropriate. What is needed between such parties is the standardization of content catalogues and file formats, formalization of the description of the datasets and methods of indexing. On top of that, new access protocols are needed that take advantage of such well-defined meta-data structures to implement efficient methods of remote pre-retrieval browsing, and subsequent partial retrievals, become more and more important.

Most notably in the geophysical sciences community the storing of files in the platform independent and self descriptive NetCDF [7] format, rather than just archiving the raw originally produced data files, is becoming more prevalent. NetCDF allows for efficient description and storing of data subsets within a file. One of the Dutch primary investigators in this field has recently expressed an interest in OpenDAP as a new, complementary access protocol for the SARA CA, since this protocol directly facilitates the remote retrieval of subsets from files. A pilot enabling OpenDAP [8] access to one of the recent geophysical datasets stemming from a PRACE Tier-0 simulation will be set up.

^h Or a node of one of SARA’s compute or visualization facilities, if that is more appropriate for the data set at hand.

2. Storage and long term preservation of data at SNIC

2.1. The Swestore National Storage Initiative

Swestore is a Swedish national storage service on the infrastructure level, making storage space available over the internet for academics through an application procedure to the Swedish Research Council (VR). Swestore also aims to provide the means for convenient sharing of research data at the discretion of the scientists owning the data.

The Swestore effort addresses the increasing need for long term archival storage brought on by mandated retention time on availability of raw research data, in combination with the ever increasing size and rate of research data produced. Swestore also aims to address data sharing problems in joint research efforts where large data sets needs sharing.

The aim of the Swestore nationally accessible storage is also to build a robust, flexible and expandable system of general use for most cases where access to large scale storage is needed. To the user it has the appearance of a single large logical file system while physically the data is distributed across all six SNIC centres. The data distribution brings the advantages of, among other things, locality and cache effects. SweStore is also intended to form the base for future Swedish participation in the Collaborative Data Infrastructure of EUDAT [9].

As a project, Swestore national storage is in its early production phase with several things being in a state of flux or yet to be decided. However, the current status of the SweStore National Storage project is described. Storage costs, strategies for data lifetime management and data integrity and availability issues are discussed.

2.2. Swestore Organization

Any long term data storage solution need to address the issues of file format changes and changes in the underlying software and hardware stack during the life span of data, as well as transitions to emerging storage technologies. Since these two aspects are not dependent, they can be decoupled to good advantage. Chiefly, this decoupling has the advantage of letting the experts of scientific disciplines cater to the different needs of their respective scientific communities as they evolve in terms of content, file formats and meta data, as well as leaving the technical considerations involved in storage to storage experts. Reflecting this, scientific expert community groups have been formed adjoined to SweStore in addition to a previously existing SNIC storage experts group.

The Swestore storage group consists of storage specialists from all six Swedish academic HPC centers within SNIC. The focus of this group is storage technology, both on the hardware and software side. The list of responsibilities ranges from operating disk and tape storage pools within the dCache back-end to the access protocols, clients and associated services of the front-end.

As mentioned, adjoined to the storage group within SNIC there are scientific expert community groups, whose responsibility lies in gatekeeping, i.e. deciding which data formats are allowed to be stored as well as gathering metadata about the data allowing systematic book keeping providing a fall back route for orphaned data, i.e. data with no owner. The data itself is always owned by the individual scientist storing data in SweStore.

The current state of affairs within Swestore pertaining to the division of responsibilities leaves virtually all aspects of long term accessibility of data outside the purely technical for the scientific community expert groups to decide. The storage technical expertise within SweStore has taken on a purely advisory role. The advice given so far bearing consideration have mainly been regarding best practices in terms of data integrity and validation and data availability strategies in terms of file formats. A depiction of the responsibilities of each group can be seen in figure 5 below.

Figure 5. Schematic drawing of the information and data flows within SweStore.

As shown in the above figure, a line is drawn in terms of responsibilities between the core storage services and the outward facing services. All decisions regarding data vetting and meta data book keeping and publication is the realm of the scientific expert communities, while the technical decisions are handled by the SweStore storage group. The intended data and information flow is that the scientist needing storage applies for this to an allocation committee. Provided the application is granted, meta data about the data set is submitted to the scientific expert group to the extent required by the scientific expert community group in question and data is then directly uploaded via the ARC [10] client middleware tools to the distributed dCache storage pools. Currently the ARC client middleware is the only route supported to upload data to Swestore.

Read access is intended to go via the storage services layer in figure 5, although it is currently only accessible via WebDAV or the ARC client, the possible means of access follow those that dCache provides.

In figure 6, shown in blue are currently available access protocols, while yellow marks access protocols under development to interface with the dCache back-end and orange marks candidates under evaluation or investigation for data type services.

2.3. Scientific Communities

Five scientific community expert groups have been officially formed; environment and climate – ECDS, the humanities – (SND HM), WLCG, Bio-imaging and Proteomics (several groups), where ECDS [11] have come farthest at this point in time and whose web services is the best current representation of the intended direction for the data services part of Swestore. ECDS presents pertinent meta data on its web site on the data sets store within SweStore as submitted by the scientists owning the data. The metadata includes the obvious contact information to the data owner as well as information such as whether it is experimental data or simulations, collection dates for experiments and instruments etc.

The technical expert group within SweStore have decided to leave all decisions regarding what metadata about stored data sets to the community representatives but have given general advise outlined below, and will provide technical support implementing necessary tools.

Figure 6. Currently available access protocols to SweStore. Blue represent current status. Yellow and orange are under development or investigation.

To ensure future access to the data it should be validated before it ends up on the long term storage medium. This validation step pertains in particular to the container format but it is good if this also extends to the content. The level of validation is entirely left at the discretion of the scientific expert group, possibly after some technical feasibility survey.

Fully automated tools will be essential as data volumes become ever larger in order to scale, especially considering the amount of data produced in present and future Tier-0 and Tier-1 computing facilities.

All long term data stored should be interpretable by applications or software stacks available at all points in time during the life span of the data. Non-interpretable data is dead data and is consequently of very little use. There is obviously a multitude of ways the interpretability can be achieved. For openly specified formats, data can always be accessible by means of conversion to newer versions of the same formats or perhaps even other formats, in cases where conversion between them can be deemed sufficiently loss free. Needless to say, proper tools must be available to carry out the conversion.

It is also conceivable that the data stored has associated applications needed for data access available along with it. It then becomes a matter of having a compute platform available which supports running the application in question. With open source software this is not so much an issue as with proprietary software, open codes can most often be ported to new platforms. When this is not an option, virtual machine images containing the entire software stack needed to access the data can work as a route to access data not accessible by other means. This works under the assumption that these images work on hardware and operating systems available at the time.

2.4. Storage Technology

The SweStore National Storage infrastructure is implemented using the distributed storage solution dCache [12]. It currently holds 300 TB of replicated user data, using a total of 600 TB. The current total capacity is 1200 TB in Swestore, all online in dCache disk pools.

The core services of the system are located at HPC2N at Umeå University. There are over 65 online storage pools (as of November 2011) attached to the system, which are spread between the SNIC centres at Lunarc, C3SE, NSC, PDC, Uppmax and HPC2N. A file upload usually go directly from the source to one of the storage pools without passing the core service giving a high aggregated transfer performance to the system. All files in the SNIC part of storage are replicated to a different site for availability reasons. With the exception of the core services, an entire site can be offline without any loss of functionality for SweStore.

There are several access protocols for SweStore National Storage. The primary ones being the SRM and WebDAV protocols, but access can be made by any means supported by dCache, see figure 6. Authentication for Swestore write (and read) access is carried out by means of X.509 certificates and anonymous read only access data is made publically available at the discretion of the data owner.

There are no backups of data on SweStore. The files are replicated between sites to minimize the risk of data loss due to hardware problems. But if the end user deletes a file it will be lost. Future improvements in the pipeline for dCache may provide a waste basket functionality which could minimise damage of end user mistakes.

There is currently no tape backend attached to SweStore, but this is subject to change in the future. Tape storage in the Swestore context would be used for archiving data not being accessed frequently as the on-line nature of disk storage is considered highly desirable and one of SweStore purposes is to act as a file system of general use.

An important feature of Swestore access is that staging data in and out from grid clusters with the ARC middleware client works out of the box. Instead of copying data to the clusters and then copying the results out again you can let ARC do that for you. Just specify the input file URLs you need and let ARC do the work for you.

3. Storage and long term preservation of data at CINES

3.1. The CINES Jade infrastructure

CINES operates state of the art computer services in high-performance computing (Jade supercomputer ranked 24 in the Top500 as of June 2011), long term data and digital document preservation (CINES is the national center for the archive of digital PhD theses from French universities and PAC, the CINES preservation platform, stores 15TB of scientific data as of November 2011) as well as the hosting of computer equipments.

The center provides researchers from universities and public research institutes with high performance parallel computing platforms. The staff of the HPC department at CINES makes hardware and software available to the users and provides specific assistance for research modelling. Research domains are classified in thematic committees:

- Environment
- Fluid dynamics, reactive fluids, complex fluids
- Biomedical simulation and health care
- Astrophysics and geophysics
- Theoretical physics and plasmas
- Computer science, algorithmic, mathematics
- Ordered molecular systems and biology
- Quantum chemistry and molecular modeling
- Physics chemistry and matter properties
- New applications and compute related applications

The main HPC cluster – Jade – is a SGI Altix ICE 8200, a scalar, parallel supercomputer capable of a Rmax of 267 Tflops/s. Jade is made of 23040 cores spread on 2880 nodes (each of them being equipped with 2 processors Intel Quad-Core E5472 or X5560). Each node has 30 (resp.34 GB) of available memory, which is a total of 91 TB. The 46 racks of the cluster are connected to the 12 racks of the shared file system that has a capacity of 690 TB.

Figure 7: HPC volumes generated by thematic committee

On a yearly basis, roughly 750TB of data are generated as part of the HPC research activity – see figure 7– which is the more than the maximum storage capacity available online at the moment on the CINES infrastructure which will be described below.

Figure 8: HPC volumes breakdown by thematic committee

3.2. The storage policy for HPC data

On Jade, the storage system (Narcisse) available is as follows: two disc volumes are available for scientific data, i.e. /scratch and /data, on a SGI ALTIX 450 (16 Montecito processors) with 64 GB memory, running Linux. Another disc space, work, which is fairly smaller, is only used by nodes (binaries, etc.). In addition to the online discs infrastructure, two libraries allow the storage of data on tapes.

The /scratch repository is used for temporary data, whereas /data allows the storage of data in a longer term – in any case shorter than a couple of years.

On a daily basis, the data stored on /data are backed up on tapes. There are two tape libraries for security purposes, but the same information will be duplicated on both. The technologies of the two robots are slightly different: the first one (Jaguar, IBM 3592) is faster and more expensive than the second one (LTO4), which is rather used for redundancy and security purposes. The data is thus eventually available on disc as well as on tape.

The /data environment is generally filled at 95%. When a user needs to add more information and room has to be made, the data which has not been accessed recently is deleted (as long as they have been backed up on tape, of course).

The /data environment is made of five disk drives running in parallel, and has a capacity of 500TB. When data are requested again after their removal from the discs, they are restored from the tapes to the discs (average restore speed is 200Mb/s).

The online discs are based on SATA technology, with a disc capacity of 750GB and 1TB configured in RAID6, operated by Lustre, a massively parallel distributed file system commonly used for large scale cluster computing, and NFS as a transfer protocol.

The current architecture has a throughput limitation: Lustre limits the I/O at 200MB/s per node, and there is only one node in place at the moment to restore the data. But this could be improved at a better rate, up to 600MB/s, by implementing a new technology.

The overall architecture is described in figure 9 below:

Figure 9 – The CINES HPC data storage architecture

3.3. Long term preservation

In 2004, the French ministry for Higher Education and Research (MESR) assigned the CINES the mandate to assure and certify the long term preservation of the French electronic PhD theses, as well as the digitized publications of the Persée web portal, which is focused on social sciences and humanities. After three years of conception and development, a first version of the PAC system – acronym for “Plateforme d’Archivage au CINES”, or CINES Archive Platform, v1.0 – was deployed in spring 2007, with the objectives of proving the feasibility of the concept, validating the architecture and processes orientations and integrating STAR application (developed by the ABES) for the transfer, access, reference and archiving of electronic PhD theses.

A year later, the CINES decided to proceed to an “invitation to tender” for the purchase of a platform based on the industry standards, with high volume capabilities – more than 40 TB – and invested more than 400k€ for this second version of the PAC system. PAC v2.0 is now running, under the same generic approach, thus avoiding specific developments when rolling out new projects, as they all share the same processes, infrastructure and storage platform. This solution is made available to the whole Higher Education and Research community, as long as the corpus to archive is acknowledged as national value/interest.

The digital documents currently preserved at CINES are mainly literature. But there is a strong focus on the primary data too, and a project is currently being run – ISAAC (acronym for “Information Scientifique Archivée Au CINES” or Scientific Data Preserved at CINES), with the objective to offer preservation services for raw data to the research community. The infrastructure put in place as part of this project will be based on widely used technologies such as Java, iRODS, etc. The purpose is to allow researched to preserve the data they produce as part of their use of HPC systems (among which the CINES one) during a longer period than the year during which they have access to the datacenter storage facilities. This will help them to perform the necessary appraisal, and identify the data which has value and needs to be preserved, and by extension the data than can be deleted.

In parallel, CINES is part of a national workgroup – the PIN (acronym for “Préservation de l’Information Numérique”) group – where the main French actors of the long-term preservation can share their experience; this group also involves institutions like the BnF (National Library), the Archives Nationales, or research organizations such as CNES.

CINES is also involved in international initiatives such as the Alliance for Permanent Access to the Records of Sciences, which aims to put in place a European infrastructure for the preservation of scientific data, as well as in other EU-funded projects (PRACE, EUDAT, etc.) and participates regularly to conferences on that subject. CINES has also been labelled as a DPE (Digital Preservation Europe) centre of competencies for the long-term preservation of electronic documents.

4. Storage and long term preservation of data at CaSToRC

4.1. Storage Setup

Storage at CaSToRC consists of a loosely tiered storage configuration, comprised of two main tiers: *Tier1(a,b)* and *Tier2*. *Tier1* consists of the recently added high-performance GPFS storage over QDR Infiniband. *Tier2* consists of fibre-channel based storage as well as network-attached storage belonging to specific user communities. Figure 10 outlines the storage configuration and the associated interconnects.

Figure 10 – CaSToRC storage configuration and the associated interconnects

The storage resources at CaSToRC include the following:

- Tier 1(a,b): CyTERA Storage (Infiniband - GPFS - 300TB)
- Tier 2: DDN9900 Storage (FC - Lustre - 200TB - 1PB)
- Tier 2: DDN9550 Storage (FC - Lustre/NFS - 50TB)
- Tier 2: Smaller project-owned network-attached storage systems (NFS - varying capacities)

4.2. Storage Allocation and Policy

4.2.1. Data allocation based on the classification of data.

The classification of data determines the strategy under which it is kept. This classification is appraised at the time of granting access to systems (e.g. through project/preparatory access calls). While the classification is constantly revised, the general classes of data, fall under the following:

1. “*Scratch*” is data that is either needed only during job-execution, or data that while it is reusable, it is easy to re-generate or transfer from other locations;
2. “*Short-retention*” is data that is planned to be kept between 6-24 months, or the lifetime of a project;
3. “*Long-retention*” is data that is planned to be kept for periods longer than 24 months;
4. “*Essential Data*” a replica is maintained for redundancy
5. “*Critical Data*” is backed up regularly.

It is important to note that these categories are not necessarily mutually exclusive and, in fact, they usually are not. For example, both Short and Long-retention data can be classified as “Essential” so that a replica is maintained.

“*Scratch Data*” are retained for the lifetime of the job unless special arrangements are made to accommodate users having many jobs with short inter-arrival times, or concurrent execution of jobs requiring the same data-sets.

“Short-retention” data are retained for the duration of the project to which they were granted, with an added (small) grace period of access to the data. This includes preparatory access with a typical active period of around six months and project access with a typical lifetime of 12-24 months.

“Long-retention” data are retained for longer periods of time and may not be associated with one specific project. This data comprises data-sets that are reusable across projects or belong to user communities that closely collaborate with CaSToRC.

A data is flagged “Essential” after agreement with the associated users. Since replicated data takes up more space, the extra storage usage is accounted to the users. In the case that the data is flagged “Essential”, one replica is maintained in Tier1b storage and one replica is maintained in Tier2 storage. Several other factors also affect whether a data-set is flagged as “Essential”, such as the volume of the data and frequency of updates. Out of the two replicas, one copy is designated as the “master” copy, and depending on the frequency of update of the data-set, as well as other project-specific reasons, the “master” copy is placed either in Tier1b or Tier2. Replication is automated via standard tools (cron, rsync) when conditions permit. “Long-retention” data is usually also classified as “Essential” unless it is prohibitively large.

“Critical Data” is low-volume data that is systematically backed up. It comprises *service-data*, such as data catalogs, and other important meta-data.

Figure 11 – CastorC loosely-tiered storage

Maintaining a balance between cost, flexibility and data safety, and taking into account the aforementioned classifications, CaSToRC follows a loosely-tiered storage policy. In contrast to integrated HSM systems, the transition of data between tiers is not fully automated or transparent.

Data transfer between tiers relies on either:

1. Job-associated automation scripts / work-flows, or
2. Interactive user commands, or
3. Semi-automated tools that handle replication for redundancy.

Storage is allocated to the tiers based on classification. “Scratch” is allocated on Tier1a. Tiers 1a and 1b are comprised of high-performance disks over high-performance interconnects and are directly connected to the CyTERA compute cluster. Tier 1a holds the user’s \$SCRATCH directory but does not contain any \$HOME, \$WORK, \$MASTER or \$REPLICA directories. Tier1b is attached in the same way as Tier1a, i.e. directly to the compute cluster. Tier1b holds the user’s \$HOME and \$WORK directories and mostly short-retention data. Tier 2 holds many of the \$REPLICA directories and data classified as long-retention.

4.2.2. Data Staging

Data that does not reside on Tier1 needs to be staged prior to execution. The data transfer is either triggered and monitored manually by users, performed using pre-processing scripts (e.g. Torque “prologue” scripts), or handled via work-flows/job-dependencies. After job completion the data is staged out via the same mechanisms.

CaSToRC provides helper scripts to assist the user in transferring files between Tier2 and Tier1a. Taking into account the size of the data, as well as other factors, users can employ some of the helper-scripts in their jobs or job-descriptions in order to handle the staging-in and staging-out of data.

4.2.3. Long-retention and Preservation Challenges

Longer-term preservation of data presents several serious challenges, such as the obsolescence of hardware, media faults and disasters. Further challenges, but just as important, include the disassociation of data from metadata as well as human factors (deliberate and otherwise). Besides the technical issues, there is also the issue of cost of ownership and operation. In order to provide long-term preservation, all of these issues and potentially several others need to be effectively addressed. To address these issues it is imperative that specific documented policies are put in place. While it is important for an HPC facility to have documented policies and procedures, the long-term nature of data-retention makes it all the more necessary.

For example, in order to tackle obsolescence of media and hardware, mid-to-long-term media migration plans need to be in place that take into account, data and hardware life-times, availability of replacement parts for disk storage systems etc. The *initially* low-volume of data to be preserved and the online requirements of core applications at CaSToRC (such as Digital Cultural Heritage, and Climate Modelling) that require longer-term storage, have not raised demand of a tape system (which could potentially cause a drop in the overall cost or retaining data). CaSToRC maintains a basic high-level “data-catalog” of projects, the projects’ datasets, their data-lifetime, storage allocation(s) and storage locations (i.e. which system the data reside on). This “data-catalog” is routinely maintained by CaSToRC staff whenever data is migrated. This data-catalog also keeps limited information on the different systems’ lifetimes (e.g. product end-of-life for disk arrays).

One other important issue for long-term data retention is the issue of associated metadata. For example, a Digital Cultural Heritage project stores a high volume of images and 3D data in a folder structure, but also maintains several indices and metadata in relational databases. These relational data form the basis of several services provided by this community and their preservation is perhaps just as important as the original data itself. Care is taken to keep associated data and metadata preserved with special considerations for data integrity.

4.3. *Transfer Policies*

WAN transfer mechanisms are becoming more and more important as resources attract users from remote locations. The main requirements for performance, security and even integrity are handled by widely-used Grid technologies such as GridFTP and UFTP. Via the employment of the UNICORE middleware, these wide-area transfers can be integrated into workflows to facilitate automation. As shown in figure 11, WAN transfers need to traverse firewalls and provide security and tools such as GridFTP (and globusonline.org which is under evaluation) make this possible and even user-friendly.

Data that originates from remote locations is initially stored on Tier2 disks, due to its easy accessibility from the middleware servers over NFS. The data are then relocated if necessary to their final destination.

While network bandwidth really needs to be handled as a finite resource (and is quite restricted at times), it is currently dealt with on a best-effort basis. The fact that bandwidth is shared with other non HPC-related traffic also presents problems with scheduling transfers.

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